

Advanced Lightweight Prototype High Altitude Airship: Designing and Testing a Model Airship for Long-Term Scientific Observations on Titan

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Abstract

Exploration of outer celestial bodies such as Titan has primarily focused on utilizing probes, landers, and drones. However, despite underdeveloped research, balloon platforms offer a unique opportunity to further our understanding of Titan due to their endurance, maneuverability, and spatial and temporal resolution. While Cassini-Huygens performed numerous Titan fly-bys, it lacked the capacity for extended observation. In contrast, a permanently stationed airship would enable long term analysis of Titan's hydrologic cycle, methane sources, and possible origins. To demonstrate the feasibility of a high altitude airship in Titan's atmosphere, a prototype showcasing possible designs, programming, and application was developed. Onboard systems measure temperature, humidity, air pressure, and movement. The airship uses quadcopter flight dynamics with four DC motors regulating yaw and pitch control, ensuring maneuverability and stability. In the prototype, an Adafruit Feather nRF52840 Sense featherboard controls the motors wirelessly via Bluetooth Low Energy radio. The motors and microcontroller are powered by 4 AA batteries and a 3.7V lithium battery respectively, allowing for 23 minutes of flight. The drone base is 19 cm by 19 cm, and the balloon has a radius of 36.83 cm, lifted by helium. The onboard systems weigh 220 grams. An additional 30 grams of ballast were added to achieve neutral buoyancy, bringing the total weight to 250 grams. Data collected demonstrated average temperatures of 28.6 , humidity of 27.5%, air pressure of 984.9 hPa, and changes in the X, Y, and Z accelerations. Future improvements could include the addition of a UV sensor, IR sensor, and instruments to more accurately measure atmospheric composition, as well as the use of computer vision to map terrain, identify landscape features, and navigate autonomously. Analyzing collected data would not only confirm the temperature and atmospheric makeup of Titan, but also enable insight into Titan's geological and atmospheric processes. For a mission to Titan, multiple airships could be deployed for fault tolerance and greater data collection, as their weight and size makes them easy to transport.

Plain Language Summary

Exploration of the solar system often focuses on probes, landers, and drones. Balloon aircraft would fill a gap in research, due to their ability for sustained flight, maneuverability, and resolution. This would be especially significant on Titan to study its atmosphere and Earth-like attributes. Previous flyby missions (such as Cassini) were unable to observe for extended periods, a task fit for a stationed airship. To demonstrate the feasibility of a high altitude airship for Titan, a prototype was developed. Onboard systems measure temperature, humidity, air pressure, and movement, with four motors and a helium balloon to maintain neutral buoyancy. In the prototype, an Adafruit Featherboard controls the motors via bluetooth, with 23 minutes of flight allowed by two onboard batteries. The base is 19 cm by 19 cm, and the balloon has a radius of 36.83 cm, lifted by helium. The airship's total mass is 250 grams, with ballast added to ensure neutral buoyancy. Data collected on Earth demonstrated accurate readings of temperature, humidity, air pressure, and accelerations Future improvements could include UV/IR sensors and other instruments for atmospheric composition and terrain mapping. Analyzing data would confirm Titan's atmospheric composition and enable insight into geological processes.